

Solar cells consisting of photosensitizer – Reductant for generation of electrical energy in photogalvanic cell

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Abstract : We have constructed *p-n* heterojunction solar sandwich cells with photosensitizer in a thin film of reductant placed between a conducting glass coated with indium oxide and a platinum foil. The current-voltage relations of the cells have been measured in the dark and light under both forward and reverse biases.

Keywords : Power point, fill factor, conversion efficiency, Rose Bengal, oxalic acid, TEA.

Introduction

Solar cells convert sunlight directly to electricity with acceptable conversion efficiency. They are virtually free of pollution. There are few reports¹⁻³ on the construction of solar cells utilizing the semi conducting properties of dyes. The photovoltaic effect in a sandwich cell consisting of phenosafranine in the solid polycrystalline state has been reported earlier⁴. The system generates a photovoltage of 90 mV within a few seconds. The dyes have characteristic properties of aggregation, which cause low efficiencies due to self-quenching. To increase the efficiency and to overcome this problem, we have constructed a sandwich cell with a thin film of phenosafranin in polyvinyl alcohol coated onto conducting glass (containing In₂O₃) and a platinum foil. The preliminary results⁵ show that the cell on illumination generates a fairly large photovoltage of 515 mV. This interesting result has led us to make a detailed study of thin-film solar cells consisting of dye such as Rose Bengal and reductants such as TEA and oxalic acid. The results are reported here. A detailed literature survey reveals that different photosensitizers and reductants have been used in photogalvanic cell⁹⁻³⁶.

Results and discussion

On illuminating the conducting glass of the sandwich cell containing the photosensitizer dye, a photovoltage

develops, which attains a maximum value within a few minutes. This photovoltage decays gradually in the dark. The growth and decay of the cell photovoltages using different dyes of different concentrations in the thin film are shown in Fig. 1. The open-circuit photovoltage (V_{oc}) increases with increase in μ concentration (C) of dye till it reaches a maximum for effective conversion of light in electrical energy and follows a relation that is similar to the Freundlich adsorption isotherm, i.e. $V_{oc} = KC^{1/m}$, where K is a constant and m is a number greater than one.

Power conversion efficiency of photogalvanic cell :

One of the important characteristics of any electrochemical cell is its power conversion efficiency. The *i-V* characteristics of Rose Bengal-TEA and Rose Bengal-oxalic acid. Photogalvanic cells have been investigated to estimate the power conversion efficiency of the cell. The possible power output from the cell can be obtained from the rectangle of maximum area which can be drawn under *i-V* curve. The power point (a point on the curve where the product of potential and current was maximum) in *i-V* curves were determined and their fill factors were also calculated. These data are summarized in Table 2. The efficiency of the Rose Bengal-oxalic acid photogalvanic cell has been calculated to be 1.248 percent, comparable to that of and Rose Bengal-TEA photogalvanic

Fig. 1. The effect of light on photovoltage generation for solar cells containing dye-reductants mixtures in the thin film. The dyes reductant mixtures are : (1) Rose Bengal-TEA, (2) Rose Bengal-oxalic acid.

Observations	Rose Bengal-TEA system	Rose Bengal-oxalic acid system
Open circuit voltage (V_{oc})	1239.0 mV	1302.0 mV
Photopotential (V)	1137.0 mV	1185.0 mV
Equilibrium photocurrent (i_{eq})	160.0 μ A	175.0 μ A
Maximum photocurrent (i_{max})	180.0 μ A	210.0 μ A
Short circuit current (i_{sc})	160.0 μ A	175.0 μ A
Current at power point (i_{pp})	100.0 μ A	135.0 μ A
Potential at power point (V_{pp})	1022.0 μ A	962.0 μ A
Power at power point	64.0 μ A/min	68.8 μ A/min
Rate of generation	56.0 μ A/min	62.4 μ A/min
Conversion efficiency	0.981 %	1.248 %
Charging time	180.0 min	180.0 min
$t_{1/2}$	90.0 min	75.0 min
Fill factor (n)	0.51	0.56

cell has been calculated to be 0.981 percent. Power point (A point where the product of photocurrent and photopotential is maximum) is determined by using i-V curve.

Systems	V_{oc} (mV)	i_{sc} (μ A)	V_{pp} (mV)	i_{pp} (μ A)	n
Rose Bengal and TEA	1239	160.0	1022.0	100.0	0.51
Rose Bengal and oxalic acid	1302	175.0	962.0	135.0	0.56

Where the fill factor and conversion efficiency of the cell is calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Fill factor } (n) = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}}$$

where, V_{pp} = photopotential at power point, i_{pp} = current at power point, V_{oc} = potential in open circuit and i_{sc} = current in short circuit.

$$\text{Conversion efficiency} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{10.4 \text{ Mw}} \times 100\%$$

The conversion efficiency and sunlight conversion data for these two systems are reported in Table 3.

System	Fill factor (n)	Conversion efficiency (%)	Sunlight conversion data	
			Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μ A)
Rose Bengal and TEA	0.51	0.981	1239	180
Rose Bengal and oxalic acid	0.56	1.24	1302	210

On the basis of these observations, the highest conversion efficiency was found in Rose Bengal-oxalic acid system followed by Rose Bengal-TEA system.

Performance of the photogalvanic cell :

All the two systems were studied by applying the desired external load to have the potential and current corresponding to power point. The time $t_{1/2}$ was determined after removing the source of light. It is the time taken in reaching half the value of power. The performance of cells was studied and comparative values are summarized in Table 4.

System	Power (μ W)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
Rose Bengal and oxalic acid	64.0	90.0
Rose Bengal and TEA	68.8	75.0

On the basis of the observed data, the Rose Bengal-TEA is most efficient from power point of view (Electrochemical Studies of Photosensitizers).

Electroactive species :

The various probable processes may be considered for photocurrent generation in photogalvanic cells. The results of diffusion length on current parameters were utilized to learn more about the electroactive species. The possible combinations of electroactive species in photogalvanic cell are tabulated in Table 5.

Table 5. The probable electroactive species

In illuminated chamber	In dark chamber
Rose Bengal dyes	Oxidized form of the reductant (R ⁺)
Leuco or semi dye ⁻	Oxidized form of the reductant (R ⁺)
Leuco or semi dye ⁻	Dyes

The value of K is 3.16 V, the current-voltage relation of the $p-n$ heterojunction cell in the dark is $I = I_0[1 - (V/V_{bi})] [\exp(eV/kT) - 1]$, where V_{bi} is the total electrostatic potential for the two semiconductors⁶ and k is Boltzmann's constant.

When the junction is forward biased, i.e. $V \gg (kT/e)$, then $I = I_0[1 - (V/V_{bi})][\exp(eV/kT) - 1]$, when it is biased in reverse, i.e. $V \ll (kT/e)$, then $I = I_0(V/V_{bi}) - I_0$, where I_0 is the dark current for the system. On the other hand, the photocurrent I_L develops when these systems are illuminated and the current-voltage relation becomes $I = I_L + I_0 [1 - (V/V_{bi})] [\exp(eV/kT) - 1]$, when the illuminated cell is biased forward and in reverse, then $I = I_L + I_0 [1 - (V/V_{bi})] \exp(eV/kT)$ and $I = I_L + I_0 (V/V_{bi}) - I_0$, respectively. Linear and semilog plots of the current-voltage relations of the systems are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 for the dark and with light when the junctions are biased both forward and in reverse. All of the parameters are calculated from these plots.

The In_2O_3 -coated glass is an n -type semiconductor with a band gap⁷ of 3.6 eV, whereas phenosafranin behaves as a p -type semiconductor. The reported band gap⁸ for phenosafranin is 2.17 eV. Platinum is used only for ohmic contact. The formation of a $p-n$ heterojunction solar cell is initiated on absorption of visible light by the dye molecules. When visible light is incident on these

Fig. 2. Linear plots of the current-voltage characteristics are shown for the cells in the dark (a) and with light (b) when the junctions are both forward and in reverse biased. The curves 1-2 represent Rose Bengal-TEA and Rose Bengal-oxalic acid respectively. The low resistivity of Rose Bengal-TEA compared to that of other dye-reductant films results in relatively higher currents at various voltages.

Fig. 3. Semilog plots of current vs voltage for cells in the dark (a) and with light (b). The curves 1-2 represent Rose Bengal-TEA and Rose Bengal-oxalic acid respectively.

$p-n$ heterojunctions, an excess of electron-hole pairs is generated and the electrons diffuse to the n -region while the holes diffuse to the p -region. In the absence of an externally applied field, the light-induced current develops a photovoltage across the $p-n$ heterojunction.

The conductivities of semiconductor dyes in thin films of reductant increase exponentially with temperature according to the relation⁶ $\sigma(T) = \sigma_0 \exp(-E/2kT)$, where E is the band gap for the process and σ_0 is the extrapolated conductivity at infinite temperature. The band gaps of dyes in a thin film of reductant have been determined directly from conductivity measurements and plotting $\ln \sigma$ as a function of $1/T$. The results for Rose Bengal-oxalic acid and Rose Bengal-TEA are 1302.0, and 1239.0 mV, respectively. There is an interesting correlation between

the activation energies of the dyes and the photovoltages generated in the film containing dyes. The lower the band gap of the dye, the greater is the photovoltage generated in the solar cell containing dye. Lower activation energy means that less energy is required to generate charge carriers in the semiconductors.

The use of dyes in the film increases the efficiency of photovoltage generation by decreasing self-quenching caused by aggregation. This type of solar cell using a polymer of low resistivity is important since its preparation is simple and the cost is low compared to that of other solar cells.

Mechanism :

On the basis of these observations, a mechanism is suggested for the generation of photocurrent in the photogalvanic cell as :

Illuminated chamber :

At platinum electrode :

Dark chamber :

where Dye, Dye*, Dye⁻, R⁻ and R⁺ are the excited form of dye, semi or leuco dye, reductant and oxidized form of the reductant, respectively.

Experimental

The dyes such as Rose Bengal supplied by Loba Chemicals were re-crystallized from ethanol-water solutions. TEA and oxalic acid (Loba Chemical) were used without further purification. AR grade polyvinyl alcohol (Loba Chemical) was used without further purification. The solutions were prepared with doubly-distilled water. The conducting glass coated with In₂O₃ was supplied by Nesatron (PPG Industries). The thin films (20=30 μm thick) of dyes in polyvinyl alcohol were prepared by spreading the solution of dye of known concentration containing a definite amount of polyvinyl alcohol (~0.8 g/10 ml).

The experimental sandwich cell was constructed with semitransparent conducting glass containing a thin film of dye in polyvinyl alcohol and a platinum foil by using spring clips. The construction of the sandwich cell and the experimental set-up were described in an earlier paper⁵. A tungsten lamp (220 V, 300 W) served as light source and had an intensity of 30 mW cm⁻². The photovoltage and photocurrent were measured with a Keithley model 642 electrometer and a model 196 multimeter, respectively

Conclusion :

Photogalvanic cells are low cost due to the use of a dye, which are cheap and used in minute quantities reductant like ascorbic acid, is also not that very expensive. So overall working with a photogalvanic cell has a lot of scope for its development.

On the basis of observation in the whole study it is concluded that photogalvanic cells are better option for solar energy conversion and storage. Also this systems with better electrical out put good performance and storage capacity may be used in near future. According to observed photogalvanic effect in all these two systems, Rose Bengal-oxalic acid system was the most efficient in all the ways.

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